

Vehicle Surveillance using Automatic Number Plate Recognition (ANPR)

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Abstract: *In this project we aim at developing a security application that will add various feature user details to the concerning authorities. On detection of a vehicle number plate, all the details can be accessed via the web app. Vehicle Surveillance will be a huge factor in the coming years considering the rapid growth in public & private parking spaces. With the increasing number of vehicle related crimes, the need of vehicle surveillance will be crucial. Also, due to the increasing dependencies of technologies, automatic parking spaces are more closer than we think. We have shown the way to overcome the issues above using ANPR technology for vehicle surveillance*

Keywords: *Vehicle, Surveillance, ANPR, technology, Number plate*

1. INTRODUCTION

ANPR is a recognized methodology that uses optical character recognition (OCR) on images taken by camera to read vehicle registration number plates to create vehicle location data. It can be used to store the images captured by the cameras as well as the text from the vehicle number plate, with some configurable to store a photograph of the driver. ANPR is used by police forces around the world for law enforcement purposes, including checking if a vehicle is registered or licensed. The systems commonly use infrared lighting to allow the camera to take the picture at any time of day or night. This technology must take into account plate variations from place to place. Vehicle's number plate recognition system has been an important area of research interest in image monitoring and processing systems. With the advent of high-tech cameras, ANPR has numerous applications for traffic management applications, and especially in the parking lot. Other applications include border crossing control, identification of stolen vehicles, automated parking attendant, and red light camera. For many of these applications, most of the basic processing algorithms remain the same. The aim of this project is to develop an ANPR system that can detect and capture the vehicle image. With the increase of security risk, capturing and extracting number plate can help to reduce human error.

The software aspect of the system runs on standard home computer hardware & can be linked to other applications or databases. It first uses a series of image manipulation techniques to detect, normalize and enhance the image of the number plate, and then optical character recognition (OCR) to extract the alphanumeric of the license plate. ANPR systems are generally deployed in one of two basic approaches: one allows for the entire process to be performed at the lane location in real-time, and the other transmits all the images from many lanes to a remote computer location and performs the OCR process there at some later point in time. When done at the lane site, the information captured of the plate alphanumeric, date & time, lane identification & any other information required is completed in approximately 250 milliseconds. This information can easily be transmitted to a remote computer for further processing if necessary, or stored at the lane for later retrieval.

Our project is an application of ANPR technology for vehicle surveillance

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

- [1] In the " Analyzing passenger & freight vehicle movements from automatic number plate recognition (ANPR) camera data " , the authors present the methodology for transforming raw augmented ANPR camera data into practical knowledge for city planners. Their aim here is to provide a better understanding of passenger and freight vehicle movements and stops, identifying similarities and differences between vehicle categories. They demonstrate their methodology on a case study for the Mechelen-Willebroek district in Belgium, encompassing augmented data from 122 ANPR cameras for a period of two weeks. They also look at the car-reduced zone and how time restrictions affect the different vehicle categories' actions. The findings are validated with GPS data from heavy-good vehicles in the same period. The potential of augmented ANPR camera data and promising themes and applications of this data source are illustrated through the case study.
- [2] In the " Proposal for an Automatic Vehicle Number Plate Recognition (ANPR) System in POLIMAS " , the authors propose an efficient automatic vehicle identification system by recognizing the vehicle plate number. They install the system at the main entrance of POLIMAS college campus to ensure that only the authorized vehicles can automatically enter the campus area. Once the vehicle is detected by the input sensors, AVNPR system will capture the image of vehicle plate number. An image is then extracted and investigated character segmentation by using optical character recognition (OCR). The method they use for detection of a plate number is by preprocessing of the image and using a combination of Sobel edge detection and Laplacian edge detection techniques. Bounding Box technique is used to find the number plate and character segmentation. For character recognition, OCR method is used by using template matching to compare the segmented image with the template. The system is sustainable as the camera will only be switched on when a car is present. The proposed system successfully detects and recognizes the vehicle number plate on real images.
- [3] In " Automatic Vehicle License Plate Recognition Using Optimal K-Means with Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for Intelligent Transportation System " the authors in this paper present an effective deep learning-based VLPR model using optimal K-means (OKM) clustering-based segmentation and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) based recognition called OKM-CNN model. The proposed OKM-CNN model operates on three main stages namely License Plate (LP) detection, segmentation using OKM clustering technique and license plate number recognition using CNN model. During first stage, LP localization and detection process take place using Improved Bernsen Algorithm (IBA) and Connected Component Analysis (CCA) models. Then, OKM clustering with Krill Herd (KH) algorithm get executed to segment the LP image. Finally, the characters in LP get recognized with the help of CNN model. An extensive experimental investigation was conducted using three datasets namely Stanford Cars, FZU Cars and HumAIn 2019 Challenge dataset. The attained simulation outcome ensured effective performance of the OKM-CNN model over other compared methods in a considerable way.
- [4] In " Vehicle Plate Recognition System Using MATLAB " , the authors' purpose was to design and implement an Automatic Number Plate Recognition system. The system has still images as the input, and extracts a string corresponding to the plate number, which is used to obtain the output user data from a suitable database. The system extracts data from a license plate and automatically reads it with no prior assumption of background made. License plate extraction is based on plate features, such as texture, and all characters segmented from the plate are passed individually to a character recognition stage for reading. The string output is then used to query a relational database to obtain the desired user data. This particular project utilized the intersection of a hat filtered image and a texture mask as the means of locating the number plate within the image. The accuracy of location of the number plate with an image set of 100 images was 68%.

3. OpenCV Model

For the OpenCV model, we are importing the cv2 library. We will also be using NumPy. We are also importing Imutils, Natsort, Pandas & EasyOCR. First we are creating a directory of images which we are importing using Natsort. Then we are searching for jfif format files. After this we are reading and grayscaling as well. Then by using bilateral filters, we are reducing the noise. After which we are using Canny filter to detect edges. We are finding Contours in our given images. Using the Imutils library we are grabbing contours (key points). After implementing our region of interest code, we will mask the given image & find vertices of our contours. These are then fed to the EasyOCR reader. We after all this print the result along with confidence and then we are starting to create a dataframe.

4. METHODOLOGY

Followed and formed a very basic plan to fulfill the requirements for our project:

Above is the flow chart of internal working. We installed all the necessary softwares and packages required for our project ,mainly, a way to access jupyter notebook which is an online code editor and a repository of sorts, we installed anaconda which in turn also gave us the required libraries and tools used during a typical AI/ML based project .Few key libraries were NumPy, Panda, MathPlotLib, Imutils, EasyOCR and NatSort. We then learned how to effectively use each one via watching different projects related to OCR. So our first action was to access a file of data(images) and then run it through a lot of these tools one by one to get the required data we need from each step. Our program in total follows 6steps here they are as follows. A lot of them if not most use the cv2 library and its functions(cv2is a computer vision library)

1. Read image from the given directory and convert the image to grayscale (we do so to avoid reflection error or other phantom errors and also speed up the following detection process)
2. Reducing noise using the bilateral filter.
3. Finding suitable edges that fit a description of a number plate using the canny filter
4. Then accessing the keypoint of these edges to form a shape in which we can read our text using the Find Contours function from the cv2 library
5. Using approxPolyDP, masking techniques and location of mask techniques we create a separate image for our OCR to read.
6. We then print out the extracted details in a suitable format or form a file(Data Frame) to be read outside the program .

For now we are using a very small amount of data and are working to use a data set or increase our own data pool to train the model in effectively singling out the data of our given number plate.

Below is the flowchart of updated code:

3.1.2) Flowchart of Updated code

Below are pics of some inputs we provided :

Read Only - To make changes, save a copy o...

Plate	Confidence
0 HHIZ DE14	0.456263
1 MH03DA5	0.48097
2 DLLCAFL9	0.665118
3 CG04MF2	0.721221
4 KL 19 J53C	0.889062
5 KL07 E 52	0.56447
6 BB-101-BF	0.974412
7 MH03DA5	0.522088
8 MH 02 H 7	0.773471
9 KL 18X 95'	0.594098
10 AC 936 KS	0.851827

Below is the pic of some results obtained in output :

```

In [2]: df.head()

Out[2]:
   Plate Confidence Time Stamp Entrance flag
0  Eteeees)  0.003371  14:02:07         3  0
1  KL 18X 9570/  0.583153  14:02:07         2  0
2  21 BH 2345 AAL  0.526206  14:02:07         3  0
3  XX88 XY8888  0.710139  14:02:07         3  0
4  Xx8b8888  0.212412  14:02:07         4  0

In [3]: search = df[df['Plate']=='MH03DA96LZ']
print(search)

   Plate Confidence Time Stamp Entrance flag
14  MH03DA96LZ  0.480970  14:02:07         3  1
20  MH03DA96LZ  0.522088  14:02:07         2  1
    
```

Welcome To Surveillance Owl

🔗 Is the number plate you are searching for below ??

Unnamed: 0	Plate	Confidence	Time Stamp	Entrance	flag
6	GA03MJ1011	0.7181	20:01:40	4	^
7	6J03L	0.9484	20:01:40	4	
8	K0563	0.7424	20:01:40	1	
9	MHIODV3465	0.9131	20:01:40	3	
10	MH 02 VD 2636	0.6642	20:01:40	4	
11	MH20EJ 0364	0.5043	20:01:40	3	
12	MH03AB 4567	0.8977	20:01:40	0	
13	HHIZ DE1433	0.4563	20:01:40	0	
14	MH03DA96LZ	0.4810	20:01:40	4	
15	CG04MF2250	0.7212	20:01:40	0	

5. CONCLUSION

We are successfully extracting image & feeding it to easy OCR which is accurately detecting it & reading it. The Size & color detection is accurate. Overall , this model is a robust model .

6. REFERENCES

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